

Factors Affecting Successful Implementation of Special Education: A Study of Seven Selected Schools in Mporokoso District of Northern Province of Zambia

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Abstract- The study was aimed at establishing factors that affect successful implementation of special education in inclusive schools in Mporokoso District. A survey was conducted among the head teachers and the District Education Board Secretary (DEBS). There were eight respondents including one DEBS and seven head teachers. Purposive sampling procedure was used at the DEBS while simple random sampling procedure was used to get the seven Head teachers. Data was collected using questionnaires which were administered to both the DEBS and Head teachers. The research report was divided into six chapters. Chapter one had the introduction, it also covered the background of the study, identified the problem, the statement of the problem and the purpose of the study. It further brought out research objectives that guided the study and research questions that were used to find responses to the study. Thereafter, it covers the significance of the study and subsequently gave some anticipated limitation of the study and covered the definition of terms. Chapter two consists of literature review while chapter three was the methodology chapter. Chapter four consists of presentation of findings while chapter five consists of discussion of findings. The findings revealed that there were a number of variables that affect the successful implementation of special education in Mporokoso District. This included lack of knowledge of the needs of CSENs among teachers, lack of trained teachers, inappropriate curriculum, and lack of special motivation among teachers, inadequate funding, lack of appropriate teaching and learning materials, and lack of regular monitoring of special education programs. Other hindering factors included lack of collaboration with line ministries and inappropriate infrastructure. Attitudes of teachers towards CSENs and the geographical location of the schools were reported to have no influence on the successful implementation of special education. In this research report, the researcher has tried to propose recommendations in view of the findings. These include; Teachers should be sensitized through in-service programmes on the needs of children with special educational needs (CSENs). The sensitization programmes should be organized by the Ministry of Education through Standards and Evaluation officers. Apart from that, the government should design appropriate curricula for children with special needs. Not only that, the government should also adequately fund the schools in support of implementation of special education. Another suggested intervention is to improve school infrastructure that would be user friendly. The government should also provide adequate and relevant teaching and learning materials to enhance the provision of special education.

Keywords: Special Education, Inclusive Education, Implementation Challenges, Educational Policy, Teacher Training, Learning Disabilities

I. Introduction of the Study

This research focuses on the factors that hinder the successful implementation of Special Education for learners with hearing impairment, visually impairment and learning disabilities in inclusive education. Consequently, this research report, focuses on the background of the study. It also looks at the statement of the problem, the objectives of the study, as well as the significance of the study.

Background of the Study

The Ministry of Education upholds the principle that every child has an equal right to educational opportunity. This implies that children with special needs have also the right to access to and participation in the education systems. Hence, it is the matter of fairness or just the access to, and participate and benefit in the education system be available to all. The development of education, therefore, seeks to promote equality of access, participation and benefits for all in accordance with individual needs and abilities.

Since independence, Zambia has three policy documents that have all highlighted something on Special Education programs in relation to learners with Special Educational Needs. According to the Ministry of Education (1977), the document had focused on the designing of Special curriculum and teaching materials. It was taken that the mainstream curricula should also apply to Special Education. However, due to physical or mental disabilities, the curricula materials, equipment and instructional strategies were to be designed in such a way as to enable the child under review cope with the disability.

This did not end there, in 1992 the Ministry of Education came up with another policy document called “Focus on Learning”. Regarding learners, this document focused on the introduction of pre-service training in Special Education as well as introducing Special Education in pre-schools. This document also emphasized on the need to establish an appropriate progression system for learners with Special Education Needs. According to Ministry of Education (1992), in order to counteract problems being faced by children with Special Education needs in their learning system. One of the measures advocated was to ensure the pre-service training institution incorporated Special Education component in their curriculum, so that teachers after graduating would be able to address needs of the disabled and the so-called normal children.

Moreover, the third document was produced in 1996 and it had some chapter which talked about administering Special Education. According to the Ministry of Education (1996), the guide for education of exceptional children is that to the greatest extent possible they should be integrated into the programmes that are offered in ordinary schools.

However, despite government’s effort and its recognition of the importance of education services for all, only a smaller number of children with special education needs attend school in Mporokoso District. But although this is the case, there are no Special Education programmes being offered especially for them. This does not suggest that there are no children with Special Education needs. According to the statistic from the District Education Board Secretary’s office in Mporokoso, there are one hundred sixty-two (162) children who would need Special Educational services in the District. Records in schools also show that the few children who are in school do not receive the same attention as the so-called normal children. It is with this view that the study was carried out to establish the factors affecting the successful implementation of special Education programmes in Mporokoso District.

Statement of the Problem

The factors affecting the successful implementation of Special Education more especially in inclusive schools in Mporokoso District were not yet known. Therefore, this study wanted to find out the factors affecting the successful implementation of Special Education in Mporokoso District.

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives guided the study:

- To establish teacher factors, administrative factors and environmental factors that affect the successful implementation of Special Education.-To find out from the District Education Board Secretary factors that affect the implementation of Special Education.
- To ascertain factors relating to community that affecting the successful implementation of Special Education.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study are very significant in a way that they will help the Senior Education Standard Officers (SESOs), District Education Standard Officers (DESOs) at the Ministry of Education (MOE) and other various stakeholders involved in the successful implementation of Special Education programmes to know what have been the factors affecting the successful implementation of Special Education. This may lead to applying intervention measures to curb the situation.

It is hoped that the intervention will help teachers acquire the knowledge and skills needed for handling learners with special educational needs. The information contained in this study will also benefit teachers and stake holders in a way that they will develop a better understanding of the unique needs of individual pupils in special education classes.

Further, the information provided by this study in conjunction with the interventions that would be made will help teachers to develop skills of identify, asses and place children with special educational needs in appropriate educational settings. Finally, applied intervention measures will help children with special educational needs acquire quality education as this is the only way they can be assisted to rise above their exceptional challenges.

III. Literature Review

The literature on factors affecting the successful implementation of Special Education. This is necessary as it provides the researcher with an overview of the subject by other academic works. The literature review will be organized under the following headings; teacher variables, administrative factors and the environmental factors that limit the successful implementation of Special Education.

Teacher variables that affect implementation of Special Education

One of the factors that had been identified as a limiting factor to successful implementation of Special Education is the teacher qualification. Teachers who have inadequate knowledge and skills in working with learners with special educational needs have usually failed to implement special Education programmes. Blamires and

Moore (2003) observed that recruiting and retaining qualified teachers and related services providers is critical to meeting learner's educational needs. Although Special Education teachers are in short supply in many places, the shortages are particularly severe in rural areas.

Another factor that affect the successful implementation of special Education was the negative attitude of teachers. In the study carried out by Sue (2008) on factors affecting successful implementation of Special Education, it was identified that teachers who held negative attitudes towards children with Special Educational needs did not pay attention to learners. These teachers get frustrated easily and they always find measures and means of justifying wrong doings.

Car et-al (1994) carried out the study to examine the meaning attached to disability, attitudes towards children with Special Educational needs and towards the implementation of Special Education programmes. These were related to five (5) underlying dimensions, the teachers' general philosophy about special education. According to Chapman and Stone (1989), the successful implementation of special education programmes greatly depends on qualified human resource and appropriate teaching and learning resources. This is also supported by Ministry of Education (2007) which observes that lack of resources and inappropriate teaching and learning resources are a major barrier to successful implementation of Special Education.

Administrative Factors

Supply and retention of Special Education teachers has been identified by Kalabula (2007) as one of the factors that affect the successful implementation of special Education in schools. Kalabula further notes that although so many teachers have been trained in various colleges such as Zambia Institute of Special Education, Teachers Vocational Training College and University of Zambia, these teachers have either been posted to schools where their services are not required or have left for greener pasture due to lack of motivation and other things.

Farrant (1980) also revealed that children with Special Educational needs learn consciously and unconsciously in an environment which is supportive. However, most of the schools do not have proper infrastructure that are disability friendly. For example, most of the school's infrastructure have no provision for learners who are on wheel chairs, they are not user- friendly. The school administration has not taken the trouble of making the school facilities accessible to all the learners.

Kalabula (2007) further explains that implementation of Special Education may also be hampered by inadequate funding of Special Education programmes. He notes that lack of or inadequate funding of special schools contributes to ineffective implementation of Special Education.

Moreover, Kokkola (1997) pointed out that as long as provision of Special Education remains centralised and highly bureaucratic, implementation of Special Education programmes would not improve. A highly bureaucratic and over centralised system affects the implementation of Special Education programmes in that dissemination and implementation of government policies and directives is remarkably slow and decision

making is highly held at Ministry Headquarters.

In another development, Sue (2008) observes that lack of knowledge and skills by education managers starting from the top to low level has an adverse impact on the successful implementation of Special Education. Some stakeholders in the Ministry of Education who do poses any knowledge on what needs to be provided for children with Special Educational needs have cited for providing wrong services or none all.

Another administrative factor that affects effective implementation of Special Education is lack of collaboration among professionals. Owing to lack of collaboration, early identification and intervention is not properly done as the result some children with Special Educational needs are wrongly categorised (labelled) and placed. Provision of appropriate Special Education services is also affected.

Moreover, effective monitoring of Special Education programmes is vital in the implementation of such programmes. Kalabula (2007) explains that for any Special Education Programme to be implemented successfully they should be monitored regularly. Teachers and all those involved in the implementation should be checked on what they are doing.

Environmental factors that limit successful implementation of Special Education

The home background of pupils is related to effective provision of special Education, not only direct but also indirectly. According to Wetern and Fox (1974) children with Special Educational needs in communities of more influence appear to have more family and school support, which result in consideration of wider range of support options. Parents followed by other family members, provide valuable support services through their own role and supporting activities. Morse (1979) also concludes that in the case of parents' aspirations for their children with Special Educational needs, the socio-economic status of the family has the strongest impact, even higher than academic success of children with Special Educational needs. Generally, the income basket correlates with the level of educational support given to learners with Special Educational needs. The socio-economic factors, educational levels and occupation status have a major impact on the family-status and goals on the support given to the children with

Many studies have revealed that the geographical location in which one lives or learns has an influence on his or her career aspirations. Herr and Cramer (1984) explain that physical factors such as the geographical location of the home, times have significant effect on the career choice of the disabled child.

Lovaas and Bucher (1976) also support this by pointing out that the characteristics of the catchment area do not only affect the individual pupil's education support, but also strongly influence the provision of the curriculum by schools. The occupational characteristics of the environment in which the children are brought up and learning has an influence on their career choice.

The learning environment has been identified by Jordan (1997) as one of the important aspects in the successful implementation of Special Education programmes. In the

study on the effects of the environment on the implementation of Special Education programmes, it was found that learning environment is significant in the acquisition of skills and knowledge by the children with Special Educational needs. Jordan further revealed that, when preparing or designing in intervention programmes for children with Special Educational needs, it should not solely be looked at imparting skills only but also provide a supportive environment where the child can interact freely with peers, full language-based activities and with appropriate material.

Werner (1987) also explained that the learning environment which is supportive in terms of free interaction between the children with Special Educational needs and the so called normal and between the children and teachers is vital in the acquisition of skills among learners with Special needs. The physical environment should be motivational and accommodating for all the learners. Their needs and interest should be provided for in the environment.

In summary, the literature on factors that affect successful implementation of special education stresses the following; the teacher qualification, inadequate human resource, and negative attitudes of teachers towards children with special educational needs. Not only that, but also lack or inadequate teaching and learning resources, poor infrastructure, and inadequate funding of special education programs. Other hindering factors include; lack of knowledge and skills by education managers, lack of collaboration among professionals, and an effective monitoring of special education programs. Geographical location of the learner's home or school, and unsupportive learning environment have also been identified as factors that affect successful implementation of special education.

IV. Research Methodology

Research Design

The study was mainly qualitative in approach and descriptive in nature. The way a researcher chooses his or her area of study and methodology usually depends on the existing worldviews. Every researcher must, therefore, identify with one of the existing main epistemologies such as positivism and interpretivism. The descriptive design was appropriate for the study because it had to describe the findings as they existed on the ground. The researcher had to report the findings through classification and interpretation of data. This design is appropriate to the topic of study because the researcher collected data by administering a focus group instrument to a sample of learners that was able to reveal information without intimidation from their teachers. Kombo (2013:71) suggests: "It is not only collection of information that a descriptive method can be used for, but it can also be used for carrying out a survey to find out learners' attitude towards their teachers without being known". Finally, when using this In terms of the research paradigm, the study employed interpretivism and not positivism to guide the whole research process. Since the study is largely qualitative in nature, it had to employ the interpretivist approach method because this is an approach to social science that helps to Analyse and present data qualitatively. As opposed to the positivism of natural science, interpretivism integrates human interest into a study while positivism involves researchers to interpret elements that recognise only that which can be scientifically verified (Speckman etal, 2000).

It should also be noted that the interpretivist method enabled the collection of data in-depth and explanatory information on the factors affecting successful implementation of special education in some selected schools of Mporokoso District. The interpretivism paradigm is premised on the assumption that knowledge and meaning is a product of interpretation of one's perception of the situation. As a result, there is no objective knowledge which is devoid of thinking and reasoning (Gephart, 1999). Hence, the interpretivist approach seeks an in depth understanding and interpretation of the situation by the people. In this case the perceptions of respondents on special education constituted to the knowledge and interpretation of the people. However, the interpretivist paradigm is criticized for relying so much on an individual's meaning and understanding of the world and being subjective. On the other hand, in order to reduce this, the researcher had to employ group study in terms of data collection from the pup. The research was designed in form of survey. This design was adopted because it allows a collection of small amounts of data in a standardised form from a relatively reasonable number of individuals and surveys describe the nature of existing condition which can be measured. Qualitative methods were used to analyse and present the findings because the study obtained opinions, feelings and experiences. The researcher found it fit to present this kind of data qualitatively using thematic analysis. Quantitative methods were also used to present and analyse certain types of data which was of statistical nature.

Sample Size and Population

The sample size consisted of twenty-two participants; these are one DEBS, seven (7) Head teachers and fourteen (14) children with special educational needs chosen from the schools within the district. This sample size was chosen because it provided the kind and amount of data that the researcher could handle given the limited time frame, and it also gave relatively satisfactory findings on the topic.

Data Collection Methods and Instruments

In order to collect data from the respondents, the researcher used the following instruments: a face to face interview guide to collect data from head teachers. To consolidate on this a non-participant observation check list was used to collect data from teachers during lesson observation in class rooms. The researcher also used focus group interview guides to collect data from pupils.

The advantage of interview guides as observed by Patton (2001:343-344) is: "It makes sure that the interviewee has carefully decided how best to use the limited time available in an interview." The guide helps make interviewing a number of different people, more systematic and comprehensive by delimiting in advance the issues to be explored. The researcher made use of semi-structured interviews; where the researcher did not follow exactly a formalised interview guide.

A one on one and focus group interviews that were used in this case to collect data are purely qualitative in nature. To collect data from the Head teachers, a one on one interview guide was used. The researcher had pre-written questions on a separate piece of paper that was used to solicit views from Head teachers on the factors affecting the successful implementation of special educations. In addition to this, the use of interview guides requires patience and resilience from the researcher. According to Kombo

(2013: 104), “collecting data using interview method requires the researcher to identify respondents and carefully request them to answer certain questions. The researcher and research assistants should carefully note down the answers given”. In other words, it is a means for securing answers to questions by using a well-designed form, which the researcher uses to ask questions. Finally, an electronic i-pad was used to collect information from head teachers as a way of enhancing the interview guide.

The researcher visited the office of the District Education Board Secretary to explain to him the importance of the study and his role in the study. The questionnaire was left with him for response. Permission was sought to visit schools to administer the questionnaires to the head teachers. Permission was also sought from school managers to conduct interviews to the children. The information was collected immediately after interviewing the targeted group. While the duly completed questionnaires were collected two weeks after distribution.

V. Data Analysis and Techniques

Data was analysed using both descriptive and quantitative statistics. Both descriptive and Quantitative data which was of statistical nature were analysed manually. Therefore, frequently totals and percentages were used to transcribe and analyse statistical information into tables, graphs and charts. This was done by first coding the questionnaires and compiling interview-based information. These codes and the responses were then transcribed to produce frequency tables, and pie charts to depict raw data.

Presentation of Findings

On the findings pertaining to the factors affecting the successful implementation of Special Education, the researcher presented the data that were collected through questionnaires which were administered to the DEBS and Head Teachers. In order to present the findings logically, the data have been presented according to themes derived from the research objectives and their views were presented as follows according to tables and figures below:

Table 1: Head Teachers’ views on knowledge of the needs of children with Special Educational needs:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	02 (29%)	01 (14%)	03(43%)	01 (14%)	7 (100%)

Figure 1. shows the Heads of schools on knowledge about children with Special Educational needs:

Table 2: Views of Head Teachers on training of teachers

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	02 (14%)	6 (86%)	7 (100%)

Figure 2: depicting views of Head Teachers on training of teachers:

Table 3: Head Teachers' opinions on attitudes of teachers towards children with Special Educational needs:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	01 (14%)	4 (57%)	02(29%)	0(0%)	7 (100%)

Figure 3: indicating Head Teachers' opinions on attitudes of teachers towards children with Special Educational needs.

Table 4: Head Teachers' responses on the use of relevant curriculum:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1(14%)	6 (86%)	7 (100%)

Figure 4: depicting Head Teachers' responses on the use of relevant curriculum.

Table5: Views of Head Teachers on motivation of teachers:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (71%)	02 (29%)	7 (100%)

Figure 5: showing views of Heads of schools on motivation of teachers.

Table 6: Headteachers' responses on the supply of the teaching and learning materials in their schools:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	0 (0%)	01 (14%)	02 (29%)	4 (57%)	7 (100%)

Figure6: depicting Head teachers' responses to the supply of the teaching and learning materials in their schools:

Table 7: Head Teachers' responses on staffing of qualified special education teachers:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	02 (29%)	05 (71%)	7 (100%)

Figure7: indicating Heads of schools' responses on staffing of qualified special education teachers.

Table 8: Views of head teachers on funding of Special Education programmes:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	0(0%)	0 (0%)	05 (71%)	02 (29%)	7 (100%)

Figure 8: showing Views of head teachers on funding of Special Education programmes.

Table 9: Responses of head teachers on monitoring of Special Education programmes:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	01 (14%)	02 (29%)	03 (43%)	01 (14%)	7 (100%)

Figure9: depicting responses of head teachers on monitoring of Special Education programmes.

Table10: Responses of head teachers on collaboration of Ministry of Education with line ministries:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	01 (14%)	6 (86%)	7 (100%)

Figure10: indicating responses of Head teachers on collaboration of Ministry of Education with line ministries.

Table11: Head Teachers' views on the effects of school infrastructure on successful implementation of special education:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	02 (29%)	3 (43%)	1 (14%)	1 (14%)	7 (100%)

Figure11: showing Head Teachers' views on the effects of school infrastructure on successful implementation of special education.

Table12: Views of heads of schools on the impact of geographical location of the schools:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	01 (14%)	03 (43%)	02 (29%)	01 (14%)	7 (100%)

Figure12: depicts views of heads of schools on the impact of geographical location of the schools.

Table 13: Responses of Head Teachers on the effects of home background of learners:

Respondents	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Head teachers	01 (14%)	03 (43%)	02 (29%)	01 (14%)	7 (100%)

Figure 13: indicating responses of Head Teachers on the effects of home background of learners.

VI. Discussion of Findings

The Head Teachers and the DEBS on factors affecting the successful implementation of special education in Mporokoso District. The findings have been discussed in relation to the research objectives of the study.

Teacher variables that affect the successful implementation of special education

The responses from head teachers indicated that 13% strongly agreed, 20% agreed, 40% disagreed and 27% strongly disagreed that they had knowledge of special educational needs of children with special educational needs. The DEBS also disagreed having knowledge of the needs of children with special educational needs. It was also established that neither the head teachers nor the DEBS agreed that schools were staffed with Special Education Teachers. These findings are in line with Blamires and Sue (2008) who revealed that lack of knowledge of the needs of children with special educational needs impacted on the implementation of special education programmes in schools. They observed that recruiting and retraining of teachers is critical in meeting the needs of Special children.

The findings from the head teachers also showed that there were no significant differences in their views on the attitudes of teachers towards children with special needs. The DEBS strongly agreed that teachers had a positive attitude towards such children.

These findings were not consistent with Car et-al (1994) and Sue (1998) who found that negative attitudes of teachers impacted on the successful implementation of special education. It was revealed that teachers who held negative attitudes toward Children with Special Educational Needs (CSEs) did not pay attention to the needs of such children. Some teachers believed that CSEs cannot attend school and so they cannot foster friendship for them.

The findings of the study also revealed that some head teachers said that they were motivated in implementing Special Education and the DEBS supported that teachers were motivated. 80% of the head teachers disagreed while 20% strongly disagreed that they were motivated in their implementation of special education services provided to learners. In this study, it was found that teachers were not motivated by their salaries and teaching environment.

In addition, it was revealed by both the head teachers and the DEBS that those teachers did not use a curriculum that was relevant to children with special educational needs. The responses from the head teachers were that 20% disagreed while 80% strongly disagreed. The DEBS also disagreed that teachers used a curriculum relevant to Children with Special Educational Needs.

This is also in line with the findings of Gosh, et-al (1997) who revealed that inappropriate curriculum affected the successful implementation of special education programmes in schools. They observed that inappropriate curriculum resulted in lack of opportunities and incentives for children to participate in activities that provide the amount and kind of stimulation typical of the so-called normal children. This points to the issue that children with special educational needs in these schools were adversely affected.

Administrative variables limiting successful implementation of special education

Findings in the study showed that all the Head teachers and DEBS had the opinion that schools were not well staffed with special education teachers. Of the seven (7) Head teachers, 40% disagreed and 60% strongly disagreed that schools were well staffed with special education teachers. The DEBS also disagreed that schools were staffed with special education teachers. Even children themselves disclosed during interviews that they were not enjoying lessons because they were wrongly placed in ordinary classes where they were being taught by unqualified teachers for special education. This means that children with special educational needs in these schools did not receive quality education. The study also revealed that teachers, the DEBS and learners did not agree that schools were supplied with appropriate and relevant teaching and learning materials.

The above findings can be supported by Chapman and Stone (1989), who propounds that the successful implementation of special education programmes greatly depends on qualified human resource and appropriate teaching and learning resources. This is also supported by Ministry of Education (2007) which observes that lack of resources and inappropriate teaching and learning resources are a major barrier to successful implementation of Special Education in Zambia. This implies that successful implementation of special education in such schools has been hampered by lack of resources and use of inappropriate teaching and learning resources.

On funding of special education, the responses from head teachers were that schools were not adequately funded. Out of seven head teachers 60% disagreed while 40% strongly disagreed that schools were adequately funded to implement special education. The DEBS strongly agreed that special education programmes were adequately funded. During interviews, 71% representing 5 children denied that they received material or

financial support from government not even from non-governmental organizations. While 29% (2 children) agreed that they were receiving support. This clearly shows that special education programs were not adequately funded.

Supply and retention of special education teachers has been identified by Kalabula (2007) as one of the factors that limit effective implementation of special education programmes in schools. Kalabula (2007) further explains that implementation of special education may also be hampered by inadequate funding of special education programmes. He noted that lack of or inadequate funding of special education programmes contributes to ineffective implementation of special education. This means that issues of lack of teaching and learning materials and lack of appropriate infrastructure in these schools have adversely affected children with special educational needs, and these came as a result of lack of or inadequate funding of special education programs. In other terms, inadequate funding of these schools contributes to ineffective implementation of special education.

The study further revealed that 33% of the head teachers and the DEBS agreed that special education programmes were regularly monitored while 67% of the head teachers disagreed that special education programmes were not regularly monitored. The DEBS was also of the view that schools did not collaborate with line ministries in the implementation of special education programmes. Indeed, any educational program can be fully implemented under cross supervision just as special education can be successfully implemented through regular monitoring.

These findings were also recorded by Kalalula (2007) who observed that lack of collaboration among professionals and monitoring of special education programmes in schools had an impact on the implementation of special education. Owing to lack of collaboration, early identification and intervention of special education was not properly done and as a result some children with special educational needs were wrongly labelled and misplaced.

Environmental variables affecting the implementation of special education programmes

The last objective of the study investigated if environmental factors affect the implementation of special education programmes. The responses from head teachers, the DEBS and all the pupils involved in the study showed that school infrastructure had an impact on the successful implementation of special education programmes in schools. Of the seven head teachers, 33% strongly agreed while 66% agreed that school infrastructure had affected the successful implementation of special education in schools. The DEBS agreed to the statement that implementation of special education programmes has hampered by inappropriate school infrastructure. 7 children representing 100% also disclosed that This is true schools that enrolled children with special educational needs must have infrastructures which are SEN friendly. This points to the issue that most of the children with special educational needs in these schools were affected by inappropriate infrastructure.

It was further revealed that the geographical location of schools did not have an impact on the successful implementation of special education programmes in the district. It

was discovered that 60% of the head teachers in the study felt that the geographical location of the school had no impact on the successful implementation of special education programmes. The feeling of the DEBS was that the geographical location of schools did not have an effect on the implementation of special education programmes. These findings are contrary to a 1990 survey of superintendent and business managers of small rural schools /districts which established the geographical location of the school as a factor in the implementation of special education programmes, especially rural districts. Rural location and rural district had a negative impact on special education due to isolation imposed by distance, declining economies in many rural areas.

The recent findings of this study endorsed that the region or geographical location of schools as got nothing to do with unsuccessful implementation of special education. Regardless of geographical location of schools, special education would be successfully implemented if schools were well staffed with special education teachers, stocked with adequate and appropriate teaching and learning resources, adequately funded and have appropriate infrastructure.

In relation to the home background of children, the findings show that head teachers and the DEBS supported the assertion that the home background of children had an effect on the successful implementation of special education programmes in the district. The DEBS and 71% (5) of head teachers stated that home background of children impacted on the successful implementation of special education programmes.

The above findings were closer to the findings of Westling and Fox (1974) and Morse (1979) who in their studies found that home background of the learners had an influence on the implementation of special education programmes. According to Westling and Fox (1974), children with special educational needs in communities of more influence appear to have more family and school support, which result in consideration of wider range of support options. Morse (1979) also concluded that in the case of parents' aspirations for their children with special educational needs, the socio-economic status of the family has the strongest impact, even higher than the academic success of children with special educational needs.

Normally, parents and relatives of the so-called normal children play a vital role in their children's education just as children with special educational needs need full support toward their education. On contrary, most children with special educational needs in their homes did not receive educational support from their families and were unfavorably affected.

VII. Conclusion and Recommendation

The conclusions are drawn from the data collected, on findings and analysis. The outcomes of this research report are in line with findings of other proponents discussed in literature review who pointed out that implementation of special education was hindered by lack of knowledge and skills concerning the needs of children with special educational needs among teachers. Not only that, but also lack of trained teachers, inappropriate curricula and lack of teaching and learning materials. In addition to that,

lack of regular monitoring of special education programmes is another hindering factor. Other identified factors include the lack of collaboration with line ministries and inappropriate infrastructure.

Based on findings from this recently conducted research, the researcher endorses the following as factors that affect successful implementation of special education. This include; lack of knowledge and skills about the needs of children with special educational needs (CSEs) among teachers, lack of trained teachers, inappropriate curricula, and lack of special motivation among teachers. Not only that, but also inadequate funding, lack of appropriate teaching and learning materials, and lack of regular monitoring of special education programs. Other hindering factors included lack of collaboration with line ministries and inappropriate infrastructure. On contrary, attitudes of teachers towards children with special educational needs (CSEs) and the geographical location of the schools were reported in this research report to have no influence on the successful implementation of special education.

Further, the suggested recommendations in this research report will help teachers to develop skills of identify, assess and place children with special educational needs in appropriate educational settings if seriously put into consideration. Finally, applied intervention measures will help children with special educational needs acquire quality education.

Recommendations

Moreover, based on the findings of the study, this section gives recommendations and suggestions on how successful and effectively special education can be taught well in schools where they are children with special educational needs and the following were proposed as recommendations:

- Teachers should be sensitized through in-service programmes on the needs of
- children with special educational needs (CSEs). The sensitization programmes should
- be organized by the Ministry of Education through Standards and Evaluation officers
- and also, to ensure to deploy special education teachers in all schools.
- The government should design an appropriate curriculum for children with special
- Needs in all the schools.
- The government should adequately fund the schools in support of special education
- Implementation.
- The government should improve school infrastructure that would be user friendly in all
- All the schools.
- The government should provide adequate and relevant teaching and learning
- materials to enhance the provision of special education.

References

1. Chapman, E. K. and Stone, M. Y. (1989). *The Visually Impaired Child in Young Classroom*. London: Cassel Education Limited.
2. Car, J. W. and Seamus, H. (1994). *New Perspective in Special Education*. New York: Rotledge.
3. Farrant, J. S. (1980). *Principles and Practice of Education*. Singapore: Longman.
4. Fisher, H. (1973). *Conversion Reconsidered, Some Historical Aspects of Religious Conversion in Black Africa*. In Carmody (ed) *African Conversion*. (2001). Ndola: Mission Press. 27-38.
5. Gephart, J.H. (1999). *The Church and its Function in Society*. Chicago: Clark & Company.
6. Kalabula, M. D. (2007). *Special Education in Zambia*. Lusaka: ZEPH.
7. Kokkala, H. (1997). *Providing Special Education*. Tukuru: Uusima City.
8. Kombo, D. K., & Tromp, D.L.A. (2013). *Proposal and Thesis Writing: An Introduction*. Nairobi: Pauline Publications Africa.
9. Lovaas, O. L. and Bucher, D. (1997). *Perspective in Behaviour Modification with Deviant Children*. London: Prentice Hall.
10. Mwamba, N. (2007). *An Investigation into Special Education Services offered in Rural areas*. Unpublished Diploma Research Report. ZAMISE.
11. Mouton, J. (2002). *Understanding Social Research*. Pretoria: Van Schalk Publishers.
12. Morse, W. C. (1997). *Humanistic Children for Exceptional Children; An Introduction to Special Education*. New York: Syracuse University Press.
13. Ministry of Education, (1996). *Educating Our Future, National Policy on Education*. Lusaka: ZEPH.
14. Patton, J. (2001). *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods*. London: SAGE.
15. Speckman, M.T. & Menziwa, F.M. (2000). *The Bible and Africa*. Pretoria: UNISA Publications.
16. Sue, K. (2008). *Issues Enabling Education*. 10 Uganda Eenet.
17. Westling, D. (1987). *Teaching Children with Severe Disabilities*. London: Prentice Hall.